

READY: Open-Source Framework for Real-Time AI-enabled Nystagmus Diagnosis

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Abstract—We introduce an Open-Source Framework for Real-Time AI-enabled Nystagmus Diagnosis, that makes use of open datasets and off-the-shelf segmentation models with the holoscan-sdk and webrtc. The framework aims to advance AI-powered eye tracking and diagnostic tools locally and globally. <https://github.com/ocular/ready>

INTRODUCTION

Nystagmus is an eye movement disorder characterised by involuntary, rapid and rhythmic eye oscillations which can be infantile or acquired later in life due to ophthalmological, vestibular or neurological disease [1]. Sarvanathan et al. in 2009 estimated the prevalence of pathologic nystagmus to be 24 per 10,000, with slightly higher rates observed in individuals of European ancestry [2]. Beyond the significant impact on visual functioning, nystagmus detection offers a unique diagnostic opportunity in patients with acute vestibular syndromes, with the potential for precise neurological lesion localisation, especially in emergency situations. The greatest diagnostic challenge occurs within the first 24 hours of symptom onset, when critical decisions about imaging, treatment, or discharge are made, but misdiagnosis is common due to limited specialist expertise in identifying subtle signs like nystagmus. AI-powered and telemedicine solutions have the potential to transform routine clinical practice by enabling real-time support and improving bedside diagnosis in Emergency Departments. Open-source frameworks are driving progress across biomedical and AI sectors, offering powerful tools that promote innovation, widen accessibility, and encourage global collaboration. Hence, we introduce READY: Open-Source Framework for Real-Time AI-enabled Nystagmus Diagnosis, that makes use of open datasets and off-the-shelf segmentation models with the holoscan-sdk and webrtc running on local AI supercomputers to protect patient data (Fig 1).

METHODS

OPEN DATASETS and UNET MODEL

We used MOBIUS, the first open-source eye image dataset captured using standard smartphone cameras under visible light, making it uniquely suited for developing deep-learning models in mobile, hand-held

applications. The dataset includes over 16,000 high-quality images, with manually annotated ground truth and binary semantic segmentations for the pupil, iris, and sclera [3]. We employed a U-Net model, a image segmentation architecture, to train computer vision models to segment pupil, iris and sclera [4].

NVIDIA Holoscan SDK

NVIDIA Holoscan is an open-source platform for real-time AI sensor processing. It integrates low-latency hardware, optimized libraries, and microservices to run streaming and imaging applications on embedded devices or in the cloud [5]. In Holoscan applications, tasks are performed by modular components called Operators. These provide core functions—such as I/O, ML inference, data processing, and visualization—optimized for AI streaming pipelines and built on Holoscan’s core technologies

Local development in AI supercomputers

The trained and optimised models are deployed using the Holoscan SDK, which runs on GPU-powered laptops or AI supercomputers. These systems are capable of handling not just a single model, but multiple models in parallel, supporting both video and motion inputs in real time. We also promote local development, where training, data handling, and deployment all take place directly on the device itself rather than relying on cloud services. This approach not only reduces latency and dependency on internet connectivity but also enhances data protection, particularly when dealing with sensitive patient information, by keeping data securely on the device (Fig 1).

RESULTS

MODEL TRAIN and OPTIMISATION

The models were developed locally using an NVIDIA RTX A2000 (8GB GPU) and later trained on an NVIDIA A100 GPU, enabling efficient and accurate large-scale learning with loss curves for data with and without augmentations as well as segmentation metrics (Fig. 2). Additionally, the models were optimized to match image resolution and adjusted to align tensor shapes (channel, height, and width). The workflow includes Bash scripts for rapid prototyping and deployment.

Fig. 1. READY framework, illustrating clinical need with Nystagmus, development and deployment pipelines and proof-of-concept with local AI supercomputer.

Fig. 2. Training loss curves for non-augmented and with augmented dataset with different data size (top figure). Segmentation metrics for the same dataset size and augmentation (bottom figure).

REAL-TIME WORKFLOW

Using Holoscan SDK pipeline, we set up the client pipeline that accesses the webcam through the browser, and another server pipeline where various Holoscan operators are linked together, including WebRTCClient, DropFrames, PreInfo, Format, Inference, Segmentation, and Visualisation. Hence, both client and server pipeline provide a real-time workflow that streams video from mobile phones and in the server, a gpu-laptop take the work for inference.

LATENCY BENCHMARK

We used time-stamps of each operators to measure the total end-to-end latency for the Holoscan workflow, resulted in 54 milliseconds. We used glass-to-

glass latency to quantify mobile streaming video to on-device inference, consisting on putting mobile and gpu-device together to quantify such latency. Similarly, with the use of WebRTC, also known as Ultra Low Real-Time Latency (typically under one second) and our DropFrames operator set to 10Hz, 15Hz, and 20Hz, the observed latencies were 280ms, 300ms, and 400ms respectively.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

READY is an open-source framework designed to speed up the clinical use of AI tools for detecting nystagmus, ensuring they are effective and accessible in emergency settings. We strive for seamless integration, mobile optimisation, equitable healthcare, and open-source collaboration. Future work includes developing Vision Transformer (ViT) models, improving video backpressure mechanism, and enhancing multimodal analysis to ensure accurate diagnosis across different ages and demographics.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Kaski, N. Koohi, S. Haider, A. Chandratheva, and R. Simister, "The hyperacute vestibular syndrome: ear or brain?" *The Lancet Neurology*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 377–378, May 2023. [Online]. Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(23\)00115-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(23)00115-1)
- [2] N. Sarvananthan, M. Surendran, E. O. Roberts, S. Jain, S. Thomas, N. Shah, F. A. Proudlock, J. R. Thompson, R. J. McLean, C. Degg, G. Woodruff, and I. Gottlob, "The prevalence of nystagmus: The leicestershire nystagmus survey," *Investigative Ophthalmology and Visual Science*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp. 5201–5206, 11 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1167/iov.09-3486>
- [3] M. Vitek and a. et, "SSBC 2020: Sclera segmentation benchmarking competition in the mobile environment," pp. 1–10, 10 2020.
- [4] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation," in *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2015*, N. Navab, J. Hornegger, W. M. Wells, and A. F. Frangi, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 234–241.
- [5] S. Sinha, S. Dwivedi, and M. Azizian, "Towards deterministic end-to-end latency for medical ai systems in nvidia holoscan," in *2024 ACM/IEEE 15th International Conference on Cyber-Physical Systems (ICCPs)*, 2024, pp. 235–246.